
The impact of price, service quality, product, and promotion on purchase decisions at Do'a Ibu Clothing Store in Rantauprapat

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ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>Article History: Received: August 24, 2024 Revised: November 11, 2024 Accepted: December 05, 2024 Published: December 13, 2024</p> <p>Keywords: Price, Service Quality, Product, Promotion, Purchase Decision.</p> <p>*Corresponding Author: asdiah siregar07@gmail.com</p> <p>DOI:</p>	<p>The purpose of the study is to determine the influence of price, service quality, products and promotions both partially and simultaneously on purchase decisions. This study selected a sample of 100 respondents using the slovin formula. The design of quantitative descriptive research uses multiple linear regression analysis, classical assumption test and hypothesis testing. The results show that all variable indicators meet the requirements of the classical assumption test and have good validity. The results of hypothesis testing found that price variables do not affect purchase decisions, while service quality, product and promotion variables affect purchase decisions partially and simultaneously price variables, service quality, products and promotions affect purchase decisions.</p>

INTRODUCTION

In the current era of globalization, companies are competing in marketing their products and services. which is very strict in the business world, resulting in businessmen having to pay attention to the quality of the products or services they market. To get success in doing business, of course, requires a strategy in increasing consumer buying interest. Directing consumers to be able to buy a product is a challenge and problem faced by the current producer competition. This is very related to the sustainability of the business competition that is currently being carried out, so that managers are encouraged or forced to be able to improve marketing strategies to win the hearts of consumers so that the main goal of getting profits or business sustainability from producers can be achieved.

A purchase decision is a decision as the ownership of an action of two or more alternative options. Everyone must have considered something before making a purchase decision. According to Jacob et al (2022) Purchase decision is a concept in purchasing behavior where consumers decide to act or do something and in this case make a purchase or take advantage of a certain product or service. Consumer decision-making is essentially a problem-solving process. Consumer purchase decisions can be made if the product is in accordance with what consumers want and need. The problem faced by the Do'a Ibu clothing store in Rantauprapat is the fierce competition because of the many sellers of clothing stores or other Fashion in this chain and competition in the online world, so that consumer purchase decisions decrease and sales decrease. Therefore, the mother's prayer clothing store must be able to consider what things consumers want so that consumers can form purchase decisions continuously. To overcome these problems, Do'a Ibu store in Rantauprapat continues to try to create affordable prices, comfortable service quality, quality products that are highly sought after by consumers, and carry out continuous promotions.

Price has a very important role in influencing purchasing decisions, so it greatly determines the success of flexible marketing, meaning that it can be changed quickly. Price is the only element of the marketing mix that generates revenue in the Company, therefore price can be said to bring profit to the Company. Price can be a tool that becomes competitive in competing. Price is something that is handed over in exchange for a good or service.

Quality of service towards purchase decisions. In addition to the price, the quality of service will be a determining factor whether or not to return to consumers, so the greater the consideration of consumers to return again. Service quality is the quality of activities offered by producers or sellers that occur due to interaction between producers or sellers and consumers. The quality of service greatly affects the growth and development of a business, therefore entrepreneurs are required to always make improvements to the quality of the services they offer. Consumers will demand improvements in service quality from entrepreneurs at any time, if consumers are satisfied with the quality of service, consumers will make a repeat purchase. Therefore, the quality of service greatly affects the purchase decision.

The product to the purchase decision is a set of attributes both tangible and intangible, including the problem of color, price, company name and factory service received by the buyer to satisfy his desires. One of his main tasks and responsibilities in the field of marketing management is to think about product design. The products that are made are products that are needed by the consumer, therefore the marketing department seems to serve as a "spy" for the company, which must always be observant in observing consumer needs. Those in this section must continuously provide suggestions, improvements or if necessary, changes to the design of the product, adjusted to the wishes of the buyer.

Promotion factors greatly influence the purchase decision. The promotion implementation techniques carried out by the Company have a great influence on the desire of consumers to decide whether to buy the product or not. According to Triana & Hidayat (2023:589) Promotion is a communication from the right seller and buyer aiming to change the attitude and behavior of buyers, who previously did not know to know so that they become buyers and still remember the product.

Based on the description of the background above, the researcher is interested in conducting further research on prices, service quality, products and promotions on purchase decisions at Do'a Ibu clothing stores in RantauPrapat. In this study, the researcher wants to raise the title "The Influence of Price, Service Quality, Products and Promotions on Purchase Decisions at Do'a Ibu Clothing stores in Rantauprapat".

LITERATURE REVIEW

Price

According to Nasution (2022) Price is one of the important successes of a company because price determines how much profit the company will get from selling its products in the form of goods or services. Setting prices too high will cause sales to decrease, but if the prices are too low it will reduce the benefits that the organization will get. According to Herlambang in Naomi Desti Ayu Lestari & Mochammad Mukti Ali, (2024:645) Price is the amount of money charged for a product or service. In other words, price is a sacrifice made by consumers to get a product, good or service. According to Syllabus & Susantri, (2018) The price of a product is an important factor in the purchase decision, because consumers will buy if the price offered is in accordance with the quality of the product and the consumer's ability. Price indicators include price affordability, price suitability, price competitiveness and rebates (Maulana, 2021).

Quality of Service

Service quality refers to the level of excellence or suitability of services provided by an organization to its customers. It covers various aspects that contribute to the customer experience, such as reliability, responsiveness, empathy, trust, and assurance. According to Arisandra et al (2021) Service quality is a dynamic state related to products, services, human resources, as well as processes and environments that can at least meet or even exceed the expected quality of service. The quality of this service is the fulfillment of customer needs and desires as well as the stipulation of delivery to keep up with customer expectations. According to Broto (2024) Service Quality is the action or response given by a company to consumers/customers who want to use the company's services. The quality of the company's service is good or bad, only consumers can feel it. Another way to differentiate a service company is to provide services in a way that is of higher service quality than other businesses in a good way. Indicators of service quality are physical evidence, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy (Bago et al., 2022).

Product

According to Zulkaranim & Triyonvati (2015) Revealing a product is a form of service organization offering aimed at achieving the organization through satisfying customer needs and wants. In this context, a product can be anything (both physical and non-physical). Meanwhile, according to Ansori (2015:98)"A product is everything that can be offered by consumers, both tangible and intangible, that is accepted by buyers in order to satisfy their desires or needs. In this case, the consumer is satisfied when he consumes the product and his needs can be met. According to True (2016:3)A product is an entire concept of an object or process that provides a number of values to consumers. Indicators of the product are product characteristics, conformity with specifications, durability and design (Mari Ci & Raymond, 2021).

Promotion

Promotion is one of the important marketing activities for companies in an effort to maintain continuity and improve sales quality, to improve marketing activities in terms of marketing goods and or services from a company, not only developing products, setting prices, and using distribution channels, but also must be supported by promotional activities. According to Kotler and Saragih, (2018:2) Promotion is a variety of activities carried out between companies to communicate the benefits of their products and to convince target consumers to buy them. Promotion is one of the variables in the marketing mix that is very important for companies to implement in marketing products and services. Promotional activities not only function as a means of communication between the Company and consumers, but also as a tool to influence consumers in purchasing or using services according to their wants and needs (Fajar Fahrudin & Yulianti, 2015:152). The indicators of promotion are advertising, sales promotion, individual sales, public relations and direct sales (Mari Ci & Raymond, 2021).

Purchase Decision

According to Assrory (2016:6) states that the purchase decision is the stage of the decision process where the consumer actually purchases the product. Consumers are the main actors in the purchasing process and are always the concern of producers. According to Andriani & Nasution (2023:212) explained that the purchase decision is one of the processes to decide what to buy or not and the decision is obtained from previous activities. According to Nyoman & Gita (2021)Purchase decisions are behaviors that consumers show in seeking, giving, using, evaluating, and spending a product and service that is expected to satisfy their needs. Indicators

of purchase decisions are as needed, have product benefits, accuracy in buying and repeat purchases (Lystia et al., 2022).

Conceptual Framework

Hypothesis

The hypotheses that can be formulated in this study are as follows:

1. Price has a positive effect on Purchase Decisions at the Mother's Prayer Clothing Store in Rantauprapat.
2. Service Quality has a positive effect on Purchase Decisions at the Mother's Prayer Clothing Store in Rantauprapat.
3. Products have a positive effect on Purchase Decisions at the Do'a Ibu Clothing Store in Rantauprapat.
4. Promotions have a positive effect on Purchase Decisions at the Do'a Ibu Clothing Store in Rantauprapat.
5. Price, Service Quality, Products and Promotions have a positive effect on purchasing decisions at the mother's prayer store in Rantauprapat.

RESEARCH METHODS

In this study, a type of quantitative method research is used. According to Sugiyono (2011), the quantitative research method is a research method based on the philosophy of *positivism*. In this study, the researcher will distribute a questionnaire (questionnaire) to people who make purchases at the Ibu Rantau Prapat prayer shop. Which contains statements related to the issue of this research. In the distribution of questionnaires (questionnaires) to collect data, questionnaires are distributed online with *Google Form* media to respondents. Population according to Sugiyono (2018) is a generalization area consisting of objects/subjects that have certain quantities and characteristics that are determined by the researcher to be studied and then drawn conclusions. The population in this study is people who have made purchases at Do'a mother's clothing stores in Rantau Prapat. The number of members of the population is unknown. According to Sugiyono (2018), the sample is part of the number and characteristics possessed by the population. If the population is large, and it is not possible for researchers to study everything in the population, for example due to limited funds, energy and time, then researchers can use samples taken from the population. This study uses a *non-probability sampling* technique because the number of population is unknown and can be said to be infinite as a sampling technique, this sampling is in accordance with certain characteristics such as, Respondents who have shopped at a mother's prayer clothing store in the Prapat region. Since

the respondent population cannot be known for sure, the sample size is calculated using the slovin formula:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

Information:

n = Number of Samples (respondents in the study)

n = Total Population

e = Prescribed preference (in this study, the prescribed preference is 5%)

Based on the slovin formula, the sample size can be measured as follows:

$$n = \frac{133}{1 + 133 \times (0,05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{133}{1 + 0,3325}$$

$$n = \frac{133}{1,3325} = 99.8 \text{ is rounded to } 100.$$

The data collection technique carried out in this study is primary data (Questionnaire). Primary data is data obtained directly through the distribution of questionnaires using google from which is disseminated online. The data analysis technique of this study uses primary data (questionnaire) and data analysis techniques using multiple linear regression analysis, validity and reliability tests and classical assumption tests.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The purpose of the instrument test is to prove that the instrument meets the requirements of validity, validity and reliability. The results of the validity instrument test are as follows:

Table 1. Validity Test

Variable	Indicator	Validity Test		
		Calculation value	Value R table	Interpretation
Price (X1)	Affordability	.793	0,360	Valid
	Price compatibility	.641	0,360	Valid
	Price competitiveness	.702	0,360	Valid
	Discounts	.793	0,360	Valid
Quality of Service (X2)	Physical evidence	.899	0,360	Valid
	Reliability	.899	0,360	Valid
	Responsiveness	.899	0,360	Valid
	Guarantee	.585	0,360	Valid
	Empathy	.651	0,360	Valid
Product (X3)	Product features	.670	0,360	Valid
	Conformity to specifications	.550	0,360	Valid
	Resistance	.498	0,360	Valid
	Design	.438	0,360	Valid
Promotion (x4)	Advertising	.804	0,360	Valid
	Sales promotion	.731	0,360	Valid
	Individual sales	.594	0,360	Valid
	Public relations	.529	0,360	Valid
	Direct sales	.665	0,360	Valid

Variable	Indicator	Validity Test		
		Calculation value	Value R table	Interpretation
Purchase Decision (Y)	As needed	.743	0,360	Valid
	Have product benefits	.676	0,360	Valid
	Accuracy in buying	.643	0,360	Valid
	Recurring purchases	.534	0,360	Valid

Source: Primary Data 2024

Based on Table 1, it is known that all indicators have a calculated value (*Corrected Item-Total Correlation*) > a table of 0.360 so that it can be declared valid.

Table 2. Reliability Test

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Alpha Value	Status
Price (x1)	0,870	0,60	Reliable
Social Environment (x2)	0,915	0,60	Reliable
Products (x3)	0,732	0,60	Reliable
Promotion (x4)	0,850	0,60	Reliable
Purchase Decision (Y)	0,818	0,60	Reliable

Source: Primary Data 2024

Based on Table 2 above, it is known that the results of the reliability test have a calculated value (*Cronbach's Alpha*) > a table of 0.600 so that it can be declared reliable and used in research.

Normality Test

The normality test that is often used includes the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. The results of the normality test are presented in table 3.

Table 3. Data Normality Test
One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Unstandardized Residual
N		100
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	0E-7
	Std. Deviation	1.28732488
	Absolute	.072
Most Extreme Differences	Positive	.066
	Negative	-.072
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		.715
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.686

Source: processed by SPSS, 2024

The results of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test on unstandardized residuals showed a significance value (Asymp. Sig. 2-tailed) of 0.686, which was greater than 0.05. This indicates that the residuals of the model under test are normally distributed, so the normality assumption for the residual is met.

Multicollinearity Test

The main indicators in this test are the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) and tolerance value, where a high VIF value (generally above 10) indicates the presence of multicollinearity that needs to be considered. The multicollinearity test is presented in table 4.

Table 4. Multicollinearity Test
Coefficients^a

Model	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	BRIGHT
1 Price	.252	3.964
K_Pelayanan	.259	3.866
Product	.776	1.288
Promotion	.765	1.307

a. Dependent Variable: K_Pembelian
Source: processed by SPSS, 2024

In the multicollinearity test, the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) value that is considered to indicate multicollinearity is above 10, and the tolerance value that is considered problematic is below 0.1. From the results obtained, all independent variables (Price, Quality of Service, Product and Promotion) had a VIF value that was well below 10, with the highest value of 1.438 for X₃, and a tolerance value above 0.1, with the lowest value of 0.695 for X₃. This indicates that there are no significant multicollinearity issues in the model, so all independent variables can be used in regression analysis without worrying about the influence of high multicollinearity.

Heteroscedasticity Test

To detect heteroscedasticity, methods such as the Glejser test, the Breusch-Pagan test, or residual plot examination can be used, where the absence of a clear pattern indicates that the heteroscedasticity problem is not occurring. The heteroscedasticity test table is presented in table 5:

Table 5. Heteroscedasticity Test Results
Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Mr.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	1.049	.924		1.135	.259
Price	-.028	.032	-.174	-.866	.389
K_Pelayanan	.042	.031	.267	1.345	.182
Product	.024	.054	.050	.440	.661
Promotion	-.054	.050	-.125	-1.082	.282

a. Dependent Variable: Absut

Source: processed by SPSS, 2024

The results of the heteroscedasticity test using a regression model with a dependent variable ABS_RES (absolute residual) showed that all independent variables ((Price, Service Quality, Product and Promotion) had a significance value (Sig.) that was far above 0.05. This shows that there is no significant relationship between the independent variables and absolute residuals, indicating the absence of heteroscedasticity problems in the model. Thus, the assumption of homoscedasticity (constant residual variance) is met, so the regression results can be considered valid.

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Test

Multiple linear regression analysis is important in understanding the complexity of relationships between variables in research. The results of the multiple linear regression test are presented in table 6.

**Table 6. Multiple Linear Regression Test Results
Coefficients^a**

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Mr.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	5.335	1.440		3.704	.000
Price	-.100	.050	-.307	-2.015	.047
K_Pelayanan	.121	.049	.373	2.477	.015
Product	.414	.084	.431	4.954	.000
Promotion	.239	.078	.267	3.054	.003

a. Dependent Variable: K_Pembelian

Source: processed by SPSS, 2024

From the results of the multiple linear regression calculation in table 6 above, it can be known that the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable is formulated in the following equation:

$$Y = a + bX_1 + bX_2 + bX_3 + bX_4$$

$$\text{Keputusan Pembelian} = 5.335 - 0.100X_1 + 0.121X_2 + 0.414X_3 + 0.239X_4$$

**Table 7. Test T
Coefficients^a**

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Mr.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	5.335	1.440		3.704	.000
Price	-.100	.050	-.307	-2.015	.047
K_Pelayanan	.121	.049	.373	2.477	.015
Product	.414	.084	.431	4.954	.000
Promotion	.239	.078	.267	3.054	.003

a. Dependent Variable: K_Pembelian

Source: processed by SPSS, 2024

The partial hypothesis testing in the study will be outlined as follows:

1. Based on the results of the price variable test, a table t-value of -2.015 was obtained with a Sig value of 0.047. This means that if a comparison is made with the value of the calculation with the value of the table along with the value of Sig, the result of the value of the calculation (-2.015) < the value of the table (1.669) and the value of the calculated Sig value (0.047) < the value of the Sig value of the table (0.50) means that the hypothesis is rejected. This means that partially the price does not have a positive but significant effect on the purchase decision.
2. Based on the results of the test of service quality variables, a table t-value of 4.042 was obtained with a Sig value of 0.000. This means that if a comparison is made with the value of ttable along with the value of Sig, the result of the value of tcount (2.477) > the value of ttable (1.669) and the value of Sig count (0.015) < the value of Sig of the table (0.50) this means that hypoposis is accepted. This means that partially the quality of service has a very positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions.
3. Based on the results of the product variable test, a table t-value of 2.961 was obtained with a Sig value of 0.040. This means that if a comparison is made with the value of the calculation with the value of the table along with the value of Sig, the result of the value of the calculation (4.954) > the value of the table (1.669) and the value of the calculated Sig value (0.000) < the

value of the Sig value of the table (0.50) this means that the hypothesis is accepted. This means that partially the product has a very positive and significant effect on the purchase decision.

- Based on the results of the test of the promotion variable, a table t-value of 2.013 was obtained with a Sig value of 0.000. This means that if a comparison is made with the value of the ttable along with the value of Sig, the result of the value of tcount (3.054) > the value of ttable (1.669) and the value of Sig calculated (0.0003) < the value of Sig of the table (0.50) this means that the hypothesis is accepted. This means that partially promotions have a very positive and significant effect on purchase decisions.

**Table 8. Test F
ANOVA**

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Mr.
1 Regression	130.127	4	32.532	18.837	.000b
Residual	164.063	95	1.727		
Total	294.190	99			

a. Dependent Variable: K_Pembelian

b. Predictors: (Constant), Promotion, K_Pelayanan, Product, Price

Source: processed by SPSS, 2024

Based on the F test (simultaneous) in Table 6 above, the Fcal value is 18.837 with a significant value of 0.010. If a comparison is made with the value of Fcal (18.837) greater than the value of ftable (3.11) with the comparison of the Sig value of calculation (0.000) is smaller than the value of Sig table (0.50), then the hypothesis is accepted. This means that the variables Price, Service Quality, Product and Promotion simultaneously affect the decision to choose.

Discussion

- Based on the results of variable testing price obtained the value of t table of -2,015 with a Sig value of 0.047. This means that if a comparison is made with the value of the ttable along with the value of Sig, the result of the calculation value (-2,015) < the value of the table (1.669) and the calculated Sig value (0.047) < the value of the table Sig (0.50), this means that the hypothesis is rejected. This means that partially price It does not have a positive but significant effect on the purchase decision. The results of this study do not support peeliti. (Lystia et al., 2022) that price influences purchase decisions.
- Based on the results of variable testing Quality of Service obtained a table t-value of 4.042 with a Sig value of 0.000. This means that if a comparison is made with the value of the ttable along with the value of Sig, the result of the calculation value (2,477) > the value of the table (1.669) and the value of the calculated Sig (0.015) < the value of the table Sig (0.50), this means that the hypoposis is accepted. This means that partially Quality of Service It has a very positive and significant effect on purchase decisions. The results of this study support the research (Astuti et al., 2020) that service quality affects satisfaction and has an impact on purchase decisions.
- Based on the results of variable testing product obtained the value of t table of 2,961 with a Sig value of 0.040. This means that if a comparison is made with the value of the ttable along with the value of Sig, the result of the calculation value (4,954) > the value of the table (1.669) and the value of the calculated Sig (0.000) < the value of the Sig of the table (0.50), this means that the hypoposis is accepted. This means that partially product It has a very positive and significant effect on purchase decisions. The results of this study support the research

(Rahayo Abdzul, Egus Suppandi Segat, 2018) that the product influences the purchase decision.

4. Based on the results of variable testing promotion obtained a table t-value of 2.013 with a Sig value of 0.000. This means that if a comparison is made with the value of the ttable along with the value of Sig, the result of the calculation value (3,054) > the value of ttable (1.669) and the value of Sig count (0.0003) < the value of Sig of the table (0.50), this means that hypoposis is accepted. This means that partially promotion It has a very positive and significant effect on purchase decisions. The results of this study support the research (Hidayatullah et al., 2020) Promotions influence purchase decisions.
5. Based on the results of variable testing Price, Service Quality, Products and Promotions obtained the value of t table of 18,837 with a Sig value of 0.000. This means that if a comparison is made with the value of ttable and the value of Sig, the result of the value of the calculation (18,837) > the value of the table (3.11) and the calculated Sig value (0.000) < the value of the table Sig (0.50), this means that the hypoposis is accepted. This means that partially Price, Service Quality, Products and Promotions It has a very positive and significant effect on purchase decisions. The results of this study support the research (Lystia et al., 2022); (Astuti et al., 2020); (Rahayo Abdzul, Egus Suppandi Segat, 2018); (Hidayatullah et al., 2020) All of the above variables influence the purchase decision.

CONCLUSION

The results show that all variable indicators meet the requirements of the classical assumption test and have good validity. The results of hypothesis testing found that price variables do not affect purchase decisions, while service quality, product and promotion variables affect purchase decisions partially and simultaneously price variables, service quality, products and promotions affect purchase decisions.

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